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FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN CONSTRUCTION

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Abstract: This article considers the calculation of various profitability indicators characterizing certain levels of efficiency in the use of fixed assets in the analysis of the economic activities of a construction enterprise, including the profitability of sales of products of interest to each construction enterprise and investors, the profitability of fixed assets, the profitability of own investments, the profitability of costs.

Key words: Construction enterprise, efficiency, business, profitability, investment, profit.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada qurilish korxonasi xo'jalik faoliyatini tahlil qilishda asosiy vositalardan foydalanish samaradorligining muayyan darajalarini tavsiflovchi turli rentabellik ko'rsatkichlarini hisoblab chiqish, ulardan har bir qurilish korxonasi va investorlarni qiziqtiradigan mahsulotni sotish rentabelligi, asosiy sarmoya rentabelligi, o'z sarmoyasi rentabelligi, xarajatlar rentabelligi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Qurilish korxonasi, samaradorlig, biznes, rentabellik, sarmoya, foyda.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается расчет различных показателей рентабельности, характеризующих отдельные уровни эффективности использования основных средств при анализе хозяйственной деятельности строительного предприятия, включая рентабельность реализации продукции, представляющую интерес для каждого строительного предприятия и инвесторов, рентабельность основных средств, рентабельность собственных инвестиций, рентабельность затрат.

Ключевые слова: Строительное предприятие, эффективность, бизнес, рентабельность, прибыль.

INTRODUCTION

In order to support small businesses and private entrepreneurs in the global community in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2663 dated November 29, 2016, "On measures to implement the project "Support for the Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship" with the participation of the Asian Development Bank, in order to expand lending to small business and private entrepreneurship, further stimulate microfinancing and increase the credit resources of commercial banks, as well as create favorable conditions for their development by expanding cooperation with the Asian Development Bank, "the Asian Development Bank has allocated \$ 100 million for a period of 15 years to support small business and private entrepreneurship." Such support programs are being implemented to further develop the activities of businesses in all sectors.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are an important sector of the economy, especially in developing countries, playing a major role in creating jobs, ensuring the stability of the local economy, as well as introducing new technologies and implementing innovative ideas. The development of small business and private entrepreneurship is directly related to the effective organization of the state's economic policy, financial and legal system.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Small business and private entrepreneurship analysis of existing literature on entrepreneurship. It shows the need to improve modern principles of marketing, brand promotion methods, and a flexible approach to consumer demands. Entrepreneurship modern principles of GIS. Many economists have been engaged in the development and application of these concepts. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Bayer.

For many years in our country Small business and private entrepreneurship In the field of research, which is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize scientists who have made a significant contribution. These include R. Ibragimov, YO. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results. The effectiveness of small businesses and private entrepreneurship plays an important role in the economy, as it plays a significant role in creating new jobs, supporting economic growth, introducing innovations, and developing the local economy. The effectiveness of this type of business is associated with many factors, among which economic indicators, efficient use of resources, and foreign experience are of great importance.

Indicators for assessing the effectiveness of small businesses and private entrepreneurship:

Profitability: The profitability of a small business shows how its costs and profits are distributed in relation to its revenue. A high level of profitability means that the business is operating efficiently.

Production efficiency: This indicator is related to how effectively the resources (labor, materials, time) used in the production process are managed. If a small business uses resources efficiently, this indicates its high efficiency.

Job creation: Small businesses play an important role in creating new jobs and ensuring employment. The growth of this indicator indicates economic activity and successful business operations.

Implementing innovations: By introducing innovations, small businesses have the opportunity to adapt to changing market demands and develop new products or services. This increases their competitiveness.

Reinvestment rate: The degree to which small businesses expand their operations and invest in new projects is also an important indicator of efficiency.

Financial stability and liquidity: A small business's financial stability, ability to repay debts, and ability to raise the necessary funds to continue its operations affect its long-term success.

"Profitability" (or "returnability") is a term used in economics and finance to describe the profitability of a business or project, that is, the effectiveness of investments. This indicator helps determine the ratio between income and expenses.

Table 1. The volume of preparation of design and estimate documentation completed by KK "TECHNOLOGY" in 2024

No.	Naming objects	Estimated cost of objects, thousand soums
1	Reconstruction of school No. 3 in the Garib Primary Educational Service Area of Kattakurgan city.	90 934 000.00
2	Reconstruction of school No. 32 in the "Soygus" MFE of the Urgut district	90 934 000.00
3	Providing the municipal waste landfill in Gulistan district, Syrdarya region, with appropriate infrastructure.	45 524 000.00
4	Reconstruction of school No. 49 in the Kamangaron MFE of Urgut district	87 685 000.00
5	Reconstruction of school No. 56 in the "Mangitobod" MFE of Pastdarg'om district	81 415 000.00
6	«We set a goal to build a new line from the water station with the residents of our business district. It will create convenience for business districts. We will install high-voltage cables on concrete poles for a distance of 6.0 km, two 160-volt transformers, replace the unusable wooden wires on the streets with concrete poles, and install night lighting.»	38 760 000.00
	Total:	435 252 000.00

According to the Regulation on the composition of costs for the production and sale of products (works, services) and the procedure for forming financial results, approved by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the following profit indicators are distinguished.

- gross profit from the sale of the product;
- profit from main activity;
- profits from general economic activities:

-profit before taxes:

-net profit:

Gross profit (GPP) describes the income of an enterprise from the sale of a product and is determined as the difference between net revenue from the sale of a product and the cost of goods sold, using the following formula:

$$GPP = ST - MT$$

Net sales revenue (ST) is the net revenue from sales of products after deducting value added tax and excise tax. This indicator is the profit that the enterprise receives from the sale of products.

Cost of goods sold (MT) is the company's costs of producing a product, including direct and indirect material and labor costs for its production.

Table 2. Report on financial results for 3 years (in thousand soums)

No.	Names	2022.	2023	2024
1	Proceeds from sales	538 133.00	1,606,887.17	1,056,800.05
2	Net proceeds from sales	538 133.00	1,606,887.17	1 0568 00.05
3	Cost of goods manufactured	195,758.00	883,787.95	453 452.90
4	Administrative expenses	304 232.00	346 460.00	431 437.90
5	Other expenses	1 780,00	754.51	24,494.60
6	Profit before tax on income	36 363.00	375,884.71	147,414.65
7	Profit tax	-	29,475.17	22 112.19
8	Net profit	19,764.00	325,884.71	147,414.65
	From this:			
8.1	By main activity	19,764.00	325,884.71	147,414.65
8.2	On general economic activities	0.00	0.00	0.00
9	Damage	0.00	0.00	0.00
	From this:			
9.1	By main activity	0.00	0.00	0.00
9.2	On general economic activities	0.00	0.00	0.00

Profit from main activities (As. ff) - describes the profit received by the enterprise from its main activities (construction work completed, etc.).

To determine this profit, period expenses and other extraordinary expenses are deducted from gross profit. Period expenses include administrative expenses, selling expenses, other operating expenses, and expenses of the reporting period that will be deducted from the taxable base in the future. In addition, other income from the main activity is added to this result, which is expressed in the form of a formula as follows:

$$As.ff = GPP - Dhar. + Bdar. - Bhar.$$

Table 3. Balance sheet of "TALIB BOBO AKT" LLC for 2022-2024

Balance (2021-2023)	2022.	2023	2024
ASSETS			
Long-term assets			
Fixed assets	7 477.00	7 477.00	7 477.00
Of which, production funds	0.00	0.00	0.00
residual value	0.00	0.00	0.00
Capital investments	0.00	0.00	0.00
Incomplete production	0.00	0.00	0.00
Current assets			
Working capital	44 154.24	0.00	149,985.78

Of which production reserves	0.00	0.00	0.00
Accounts receivable	402,861.49	683,865.40	115,958.94
It has expired.			
By total balance sheet asset	454 492.73	683,865.40	265,944.72
PASSIVE			
Source of equity funds			
Authorized capital	300.00	300.00	300.00
Retained earnings	1006.66	296,434.30	147,414.65
Obligations			
Loans	452,060.93	226 426.1	88,000.80
Accounts payable	6,052.55	12,080.44	12,046.97
Overdue debts	0.00	0.00	0.00
Of which, budget debts	14760.38	73,685.43	679.22
From this, wage arrears	0.00	73,813.99	17,503.08
On the liabilities side of the total balance sheet	452,060.93	683,865.40	265,944.72

Based on the information provided by the organization's accounting department and financial statements, the profit from the main activity was equal to the profit before tax. Net profit is calculated using the following formula:

$$Sf = As.ff - \text{Profit tax} - \text{Other taxes}$$

When assessing financial results, the efficiency ratio should also be calculated. This includes profitability indicators that show the ratio of profit to economic activity indicators.

When analyzing the economic activities of a construction enterprise, various profitability indicators are calculated that characterize certain levels of efficiency in the use of fixed assets. The main ones that are of interest to each construction enterprise and investors are: profitability of product sales; profitability of fixed assets; profitability of own investments; profitability of expenses.

An analysis of the organization's financial results, conducted using the data in Table 3 and the formulas above, is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Analysis of financial results of "Technology" LLC for 2022-2024 (thousand soums)

No.	Indicators	2022.	2023	2024	Change, %
1	Gross profit or financial result from product sales	342 375.00	723,099.22	603 347.15	83.4
2	Profit from main activity	36 363.00	375,884.71	147,414.68	39.21
3	Profit before income tax	36 363.00	375,884.71	147,414.68	39.21
4	Net profit	19,764.00	325,884.71	147,414.68	45.23
5	Return on equity	15.2	109.8	99.7	90.8
6	Product sales profitability	69.19	81.81	60.2	73.58
7	Cost-effectiveness	18.57	36.82	32.5	88.26
8	Payback of own investment	6.61	9.11	8.24	90.4

Table 4 analyzes the financial results of "Technology" LLC for 2022-2024. We can see that all indicators of our enterprise had the lowest indicators in 2022. In this case, gross profit or financial result from product sales was 342,375 thousand soums in 2022, 723,099.22 thousand soums in 2023, while in 2024 it was 603,347.15 thousand soums, which is a decrease of 119,752.07 thousand soums compared to the previous year, and an increase of 260,972.15 thousand soums compared to 2022. While the profit from the main activity amounted

to 375,884.71 thousand soums in 2023, in 2024 it decreased by 228,470.03 thousand soums compared to the previous year, amounting to 147,414.68 thousand soums. Net profit, accordingly, recorded the highest indicator in 2023. While the return on equity was 15.2 percent in 2022, it increased to 84.5 percent in 2024 and amounted to 99.7 percent. The main reason for this is the significant increase in net profit and other indicators in 2023-2024. Due to this, the payback period of the investment had the shortest period in 2024, which was 6.61 years in 2022 and 6 years in 2023, which increased by 2.5. In 2024, it decreased by 0.87 units compared to the previous base year and amounted to 8.24 years.

To improve all economic indicators of the organization, it will be necessary to find ways to reduce costs, carry out design work on high-yield construction, and develop a program of expenses and income for the company.

Analysis of the financial stability and soundness of a project enterprise in construction. An enterprise that covers the funds invested in assets with its own funds, does not allow inappropriate receivables and payables, and pays its obligations on time is considered a financially stable enterprise. Financial stability is determined by the ratio of own and borrowed funds and is calculated using a number of indicators: independence, financial stability, and financial dependence coefficients.

In the specific case, according to Table 4, the organization's own funds over the years are equal to the following (in thousand soums): OS1 = 1,306.66; OS2 = 296,734.3; OS3 = 147,714.65. Operating funds: S1 = 44 154.24; S2 = 0.00; S3 = 149,985.78. Debt funds: JS1 = 452,060.00; JS2 = 376,055.96; JS3 = 106,188.93. IshS1 = 0.00; IshS2 = 0.00; IshS3 = 0.00. Based on this data, we have presented in Table 5 the results of the analysis of the financial stability of the organization for 2022-2024:

Table 5. Assessment of the financial stability of "Technology" LLC in 2022-2024

No.	Indicators	2022.	2023	2024	Change, %
1	Independence coefficient (Must.k)	0.02	0.00	0.98	0.98
2	Financial stability coefficient (Mbar.k)	0.002	0.78	1.39	1.78
3	Financial dependency ratio (Mqar.k)	33.79	0.00	1.01	1.01
4	Equity mobility ((Uzsar.har.)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

As shown in Table 5, we can see that the financial stability of TECHNOLOGY LLC has deteriorated overall. The independence coefficient was 0.02 in 2022, decreased by 0.00 points in 2023 to 0.02, and also increased by 0.98 points in 2024, which is an increase of 0.98 points compared to the base year. The financial stability indicator was 1.39 in 2024, an increase of 1.78 points compared to 2023. The financial dependence coefficient was 0.00 in 2023, and increased by about 1.01 percent in 2024 to 1.01. The equity mobility coefficient was 0.00 in 2022, 2023, and 2024.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, we can say that based on the data, the financial situation of KK "TECHNOLOGY" is deteriorating, the reason being that the financial dependency ratios have been increasing over the last two years.

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